

OPENING BIG DATA FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

Review of the CASEarth
Program's Data Policy

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

SEPTEMBER 2022

This independent report was requested from CODATA by the CASEarth Program, and specifically the CASEarth Review Team, who comprise the primary intended audience. Nevertheless, we hope that government decision-makers with an interest in Open Science and data infrastructures, members of the research and policy communities concerned with Earth observation data and the SDGs, as well as data policy experts may find the analysis of interest.

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Please cite this report as: CODATA, the Committee on Data of the International Science Council; Samors, Robert; Uhler, Paul; Aitong LI; Simon Hodson; Opening Big Data for a Sustainable Future: Review of the CASEarth Program’s Data Policy (CODATA, Paris, 2022), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7085232>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

*Antarctic Expedition
by CASEarth*

I INTRODUCTION

The Chinese Academy of Sciences Big Earth Data Science Engineering Program (CASEarth) is a well-structured, well-funded research activity that is perhaps the most prominent research program now at CAS. By revising its focus to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) during the course of this review, the Program has sought to achieve global international prominence and relevance that will carry it forward through the International Research Center of Big Data for Sustainable Development Goals, or CBAS. It therefore promises to assume a leadership role in Chinese and international research on the SDGs using Big data.

A major part of that leadership and prominence can be

attributed to the CASEarth Program's open data policy and the free, online availability of many of its data holdings. These networked data have both classic public-good characteristics and support the highly important public-interest objectives that are embodied in the SDGs themselves, particularly for the Low-to-Middle-Income Countries (LMICs).

This review report is intended to strengthen the CASEarth Data Policy and, accordingly, the impact of the Program for the SDGs, the international research community, and CAS itself. It is our hope that the suggestions presented here will help improve the Program to achieve its desired full potential.

II STATEMENT OF TASK

The CASEarth Program commissioned the Committee on Data, or CODATA (see: <https://codata.org/>) of the International Science Council to review the data policy regarding the Program's research data. Information about the CODATA Consultant Review Team and the CASEarth Review Team that managed the review process is provided in Annex 5.1 of this report. The Statement of Task given by the CASEarth to CODATA specified the following objectives:

- a. Define and describe key terms used in the CASEarth Programme and internationally that are relevant to data policy and this review
- b. Describe and assess the CASEarth Programme's Data Policy, particularly in relation to:
 - i. the status and framework of other relevant international good practices,
 - ii. the implementation of the Programme's initial goals,
 - iii. the development of new data sharing approaches and,

- iv. increasing the value of the data within its purview.
- c. Appraise the extent to which the CASEarth Programme's mission of supporting scientific contributions to the SDGs through earth observations has been facilitated by its data policy and the supporting human and technical infrastructures. The review will consider whether the data policy enables activities such as education and training, data science and applications, the development of various science-ready open data products, and other scientific and social objectives.
- d. Develop conclusions and propose formative recommendations.

This task statement guided our work and each chapter or section of the report addresses a specific aspect. The review process and methodology—comprising a literature review, interviews, and consultations with CASEarth personnel—are described in Section 1.2.

III SUMMARY OF CONCLUSIONS

The Chinese Academy of Sciences and the CASEarth Program consider the Program to be not only a “flagship” research initiative but are intent on establishing a successful open data policy based on generally accepted international norms. While the current policy provides a strong foundation, there are nonetheless improvements to it that can and should be made.

Since a data policy that is as open as possible and as closed as necessary is increasingly the norm in public international research, it is important to educate data users on the rationale underlying the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Data Principles and the benefits that such a policy and adherence to it can bring. Conversely, it is essential to minimize the negative aspects of non-compliance in a realistic and useful manner.

The CASEarth platform now provides open access to rich varieties of data covering a wide range of fields and disciplines, including climate change, natural resources management, environmental conservation, and biodiversity and ecosystem studies. Not limited to scientific data sharing, CASEarth also allows the sharing of new algorithms and research models, with the ambitious goal of facilitating more complex cloud computing and online data analysis. Further improvement is needed to comply with the FAIR Data Principles, especially the interoperability and reusability principles, to facilitate access to and reuse of CASEarth datasets and data products by internal and external users.

There are many institutions worldwide engaged in Earth science research. Nevertheless, the CASEarth subject-matter focus is appropriate and well targeted, particularly regarding the emphasis on the UN's Sustainable Development Goals from a Big Earth and environmental data perspective, and will become even more so in the next phase of the Program. This is an area of critical importance in which few players are involved from a Big data standpoint. There also is room for improvement in the greater coordination of research objectives and data activities with other relevant groups in order to take advantage of synergies, minimize redundancies, and maximize the utilization of CASEarth

data—a key outcome of an effective data policy.

Compared with some conventional platforms run by foreign entities, this new platform in China stands out as the first to target the SDGs with some unique datasets and advanced algorithms to support decision-making in sustainable development. Domestically, the Program has received increasing support after China reaffirmed its commitment to the SDGs. Internationally, CASEarth not only benefits from China's Belt and Road Initiative through strengthened local collaborations, but also holds the potential to provide Big data support to developing countries.

Due to its relatively short history, CASEarth's methods of collecting, storing, sharing, and processing data will need continuous improvement even beyond the completion of the current Program. Building up data standardization systems for non-satellite data remains a complex problem that requires innovative solutions. Improved data categorization and data recommendation systems are necessary to ensure that the data can be quickly found by its potential users.

Good communication between engineers/technicians and scientists is crucial to identify further potential applications of data resources, enriching metadata with more accurate attributes, adjusting data formats and grid sizes, and enhancing the interoperability between satellite and non-satellite data. More effort is required to improve the English version of the data platform and the data products to allow foreign users to find, access, and reuse these data.

From the individual user perspective, foreign interviewees who worked with Chinese collaborators were generally very positive in their comments and impressions of CASEarth and the Chinese data resources they were using. It was not always clear, however, whether the data sets being referenced had been obtained directly through the CASEarth platform or through direct collaborations with Chinese colleagues. Many of the non-Chinese interviewees were either aware of CASEarth but had never tried to access its data resources or were unaware of the capacity that exists through CASEarth.

*Glimmer Satellite
Image of Beijing by
CASEarth*

Among both groups, there was limited knowledge of the CASEarth Data Policy. Any familiarity was often only the result of the CODATA Consultant Review Team having provided a translation of the policy prior to the interview. There were numerous calls for more active communication and dissemination on the part of CASEarth, especially in terms of making the data policy and other resources available in English, and for CASEarth to make a greater effort to raise its visibility in the international community. At the same time, CASEarth received high praise for its efforts and intention to make its data products open and accessible, even among those who were unfamiliar with CASEarth's capabilities.

Finally, the short courses for selected young researchers from LMICs, as well as online training modules, are primarily or exclusively focused on the scientific and technical aspects of research data and their use. The underlying rationale for a policy that emphasizes the FAIR Data Principles and the sharing and reuse of scientific data as much as possible is not being promoted systematically. While researchers do not need to be data policy experts, they should understand that rationale and approach to be successful in their work, particularly in furthering the goals of the CASEarth Program, the SDGs, and generally being good citizens.

IV SUMMARY OF RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations below are all directed to the CASEarth Program managers to decide how best to implement them, unless more specific actors are named. Also, the time for implementation is noted either in the near term, which means as soon as practicable but not later than the end of the current CASEarth Program, or in the longer term, for CBAS, which will take over the infrastructure and continue to provide

data services of CASEarth after its completion. The recommendations focus on both the CASEarth Data Policy and some programmatic aspects of the Program, as they are inextricably linked. Further development and implementation of the data policy and improvements in particular program elements are necessary to ensure its successful implementation.

IV.A. RECOMMENDATIONS TO IMPROVE THE IMPLEMENTATION AND EFFECTIVENESS OF THE CASEARTH PROGRAM'S RESEARCH DATA POLICIES

1. Based on the rationale presented throughout this study, we commend the CASEarth Program for adopting a default rule of openness for its data resources, subject only to legitimate and justified restrictions. The data policy should take advantage of and accentuate the positive underlying rationale and minimize the negative effects it might have. The areas that ought to be considered in developing the policy further are multidimensional, as outlined throughout this report, and should be reviewed internally periodically.

The CASEarth Program's Data Policy should encompass not only the open use of data and data products available through the Data Sharing and Service Portal (and its CBAS-based successor), but also the open aspects of data collection/submission, data analysis, and data processing by data owners and users outside of the CASEarth Program.

In addition, the CASEarth Program should work with other research projects and organizations across the Chinese government to standardize open data policies.
2. The CASEarth Program needs to publish its data policy (not just its data license) on its website, in both the Chinese and English versions, in order to promote visibility, transparency, and compliance.
3. Any changes made in the existing data policy need to be fully substantiated and justified so that there will be understanding and respect by those who need to subsequently implement and abide by it. Such changes should be made with the data user perspectives in mind.

Although there are some examples and anecdotal information that support the existing data policy, the CASEarth Program may wish to undertake several pilot projects to demonstrate to the public, policymakers, and funders the effects of an open and FAIR data policy. In this regard, CASEarth should analyze various "use cases" both inside and outside China in order to improve its data sharing policy, including its privacy protections.
4. Because "ownership" of the data policy is important to improve its effectiveness and subsequent compliance, key representatives of major stakeholder groups should be involved in the continuing development and implementation of the CASEarth Program's data policy.
5. Promoting compliance with the data policy should include a mix of incentives and penalties that are specifically targeted at the category of data providers and users in question.
6. In order to positively promote the data policy and its benefits, a selection of prizes and professional recognition should be implemented that each year reward the individuals, both within and external to China, who demonstrate the most creativity and productivity in using and disseminating the CASEarth Program's data for research and public interest uses.
7. The researcher or educator from outside of the government and business who uses any civil government Earth observation data, including CASEarth Program data, in a publication should deposit the data that underpin the results of the research in an open, public repository that is approved by CASEarth/CBAS or, at a minimum, make such data available upon request after publication or within a specified period. To help enforce compliance with this recommendation, the researcher or educator must demonstrate that the supporting data were made available.
8. We also commend the CASEarth Program for further focusing its research goals on the SDGs, thereby making the results of the research more socially and internationally useful and relevant. If the SDGs are extended beyond 2030, then CBAS should be extended as well.
9. Because environmental observational data increase in value the longer that they are collected, ideally in a consistent manner, they are useful for documenting long-term changes to the environment. The data collected under the Program's auspices therefore should not only be preserved, including sufficient backup, and continue to be made openly available as much as possible, but the research results, infrastructure, and data policy should be closely coordinated with and used as appropriate for any follow-on research to make sure that the investments in the existing CASEarth Program are fully utilized.
10. The CASEarth Program and its successor, the CBAS, should review its activities from a duplication of effort and coordination perspective on an annual basis, both in China and internationally.

IV.B. RECOMMENDATIONS TO ENSURE GREATER BENEFIT TO USERS OF CASEARTH DATA RESOURCES

1. The CASEarth Program should place more emphasis on providing data products, rather than raw data, that could support decision-making related to the UN SDGs. While we recognize that there exist different preferences among researchers, we believe that providing more data products concerned with the SDGs will help distinguish the CASEarth Data Sharing and Service Portal from other international data providers and increase the prominence of CASEarth and CBAS.

Further, the Program should continuously explore the potential broad value of its data products not only for academic communities but also for governmental and non-governmental institutions. It is essential for the Program to have some flagship data products that can support cutting-edge research and policymaking related to the SDGs.

2. The CASEarth Program should continue to improve the interoperability of its datasets, especially between satellite and non-satellite data. The Program ought to integrate data from multiple sources, rather than focusing only on remote sensing data with non-satellite data playing a complementary role.
3. Further enrichment and better scrutiny of metadata will be crucial to strengthen the reusability of the Big Earth Data. The CASEarth Program has devoted substantial effort to control data quality through external reviews. However, there are still concerns with inconsistent review standards. To make the data reusable, the metadata should be richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. CASEarth also should develop more detailed and discipline-specific metadata specifications, including object description, date and time when the data was collected, and data collection method description, especially for raw data. Having a time stamp on data with the latest updated information also would be very useful.
4. The CASEarth Program should enhance the English version of the data sharing platform to strengthen the implementation and effectiveness of the Program's Data Policy. Limited English translation constrains the capacity of foreign users to find and access scientific data provided by the

CASEarth's Data Sharing and Service Portal. This situation directly impacts the ability of CASEarth to successfully implement its data policy, especially internationally. Increasing the number of data management scientists could be one solution to solve the communication problems. These would be professionals who can work as brokers between engineers/technicians building the portal and scientists from specific fields.

5. The CASEarth Program should continue to refine and improve the data access portal through additional actions, including: increasing the amount of data and information being made available; increasing the depth and breadth of data available in specific scientific areas; expanding the availability of data and data products relating to areas outside of China; and making the Data Sharing and Service Portal registration process as simple as possible.
6. Policymakers and funders need to ensure the long-term viability/sustainability of the CASEarth/CBAS and its data resources. The full value of the Program hinges on its sustainability.

Moreover, the continued success of the Program rests on the continued development of an open data culture in China. Improved incentive mechanisms are needed, including recording and publicizing data citations, carrying out periodical citation reviews, launching scientific data journals, and tracking the use of data products by policy and decision makers.

7. CASEarth managers need to address technical issues regarding CASEarth webpages and links between the CASEarth homepage and the Data Sharing and Service Portal, including: repairing broken links and fixing information on webpages displayed from dropdown menus.
8. CASEarth managers should increase the visibility and utilization of the CBAS/CASEarth Data Sharing and Service Portal (including cloud services) by: 1) participating in international symposia and conferences as attendees and presenters, and through sponsorship of display booths and other publicly accessible activities at appropriate meetings; and 2) increasing partnerships with international data organizations.

*Blue Ice in Antarctic
by CASEarth*

CODATA

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